

Openness To Experience And Its Relationship To Self-Determination Of Volleyball Coaches In Iraq

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Abstract

The study aimed to build and legalize the two measures of openness to experience and self-control of volleyball coaches in Iraq and to identify the relationship between them. As for the third chapter, in which the researchers used the descriptive approach using the survey study method, the research community represented the (180) volleyball coaches in Iraq. They were divided into a building sample consisting of (100) trainers and an application sample of (60) trainers. As for the fourth chapter, it included presenting, analyzing and discussing the results regarding the application of the two study measures and the nature of the relationship between them. As for the fifth chapter, it was one of the most important conclusions. The experience and self-control of volleyball coaches and the most important recommendations are the adoption of these two measures to measure openness to the experience and self-control of volleyball coaches.

Introduction

The biggest aspect of the training process falls on the shoulders of the coach, who should be open to experience in order to acquire skills and knowledge, and be self-control towards the players' inappropriate behavior, especially after the change and openness that affected the segments of society, including the trainers segment, after the improvement of the standard of living for coaches And the clear increase in their income has become easier for them to access the Internet or buy various books, which have the most important and influential role in providing coaches with new skills and experiences that help them in managing teams and delivering sufficient information to the players, and the importance of studying openness to experience and self-control of coaches increases in light of The current challenging circumstance, and the psychological conflicts that individuals are exposed to at the present time as a result of their impulses towards ambitions on the one hand and as a result of life's difficulties and instability.

Research problem:

The coach who has a self that is not open and identical with the cultural system or cultural identity in which that individual lives, he suffers from maladaptation, because the self is a mechanism that enables him to conform to the social and sports environment, and that the temporal structures of the coach must be consistent or compatible with the cultural system in which he interact Otherwise, the coach will feel uneasy and isolated due to his inability to develop his behavioral, motivational and emotional processes and his lack of openness and interaction with players in the culture, social and sports context.

Research Objectives:

1. Building and codifying the two measures of openness to experience and self-control of volleyball coaches in Iraq.
2. Knowing the relationship between openness to experience and self-control of volleyball coaches in Iraq.

Research areas:

1. The human field: coaches of volleyball clubs in Iraq for the 2019-2020 sports season
2. Time domain: 9/15/2019 until 1/15/2020
3. Spatial domain: stadiums and club sports halls in Iraq.

Research methodology and field procedures:

Research Methodology

1. The researchers used the descriptive approach using the survey method, which is the method used by the researchers to obtain adequate and accurate information depicting the social reality that affects all activities (4: 132).
2. The research community and its sample: It is all the individuals who are the subject of the problem. Thus, the research community included coaches for volleyball clubs in Iraq, who numbered (180)

coaches, and the research sample consisted of (160) coaches, meaning (88.88%), and was divided into a building sample of (100) coaches. The application sample (60) trainers and the pilot sample (10) trainers from outside the original sample.

Field research procedures:

Procedures for building the two measures of openness to experience and self-control: In order to reach the results of the current research, its objectives must be achieved, which is building the two measures of openness to experience and self-control of volleyball coaches. For the purpose of achieving this, the researchers followed the following steps:

1. Determining the objective of the scale: The goal of building the scale is to identify the openness to experience and self-control of volleyball coaches in Iraq.
2. Determining the fields of the two scales: in order to divide the scale into its initial titles so that each axis represents a specific field, and after reviewing the scientific sources and references, researchers were able to identify six basic areas of the scale of openness to experience, which are (mental development, various activities, feelings, beauty, imagination, and values) As for the self-control scale, five areas were identified (the ability to control, effectiveness, reinforcement, good behavior with the decisions of the rulers, the ability to face difficulties). % Or more, that is, by (12) experts out of (16) experts, so two fields were excluded from the scale of openness to experience (beauty and values examination). As for the measure of self-control, the field of (ability to face difficulties) was excluded.
3. Preparing the initial formula for the two scales: The researchers drafted (68) paragraphs for the openness to experience scale that are compatible with the nature and purpose of the scale, and (60) paragraphs for the self-control scale.

Present the initial formula for the two measures to the arbitrators:

After the experts and specialists expressed their responses and observations on the paragraphs of the scale, it appeared that the paragraphs agreed upon by (75%) or more than the experts and specialists are considered acceptable, that is, by (12) experts out of (16) experts, and the final analysis resulted in the acceptance of (63) paragraphs For the scale of openness to experience and (54) paragraphs for the scale of self-control. The validity of the ladder was confirmed after its presentation to the experts with five alternatives: (Strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, strongly agree) noting that the paragraphs were formulated in two positive and negative directions and weight was given to the paragraphs (1, 5).

Procedures for applying the two scales to the building sample: Then the researchers applied the two scales to the construction sample of (100) trainers, and after completing the process of distributing the forms and answering them, the researchers checked each form to ensure that all the paragraphs were answered correctly.

Statistical analysis of paragraphs:

First: The strength of paragraph discrimination: Distinguishing power is defined as the ability of the paragraph to distinguish between individuals who obtain high scores and individuals who obtain low scores in the trait measured by the scale (7: 258).

For the purpose of finding the discriminatory strength of the paragraphs after obtaining the sample answers for the two scales, the (T-Test) test was used for the purpose of distinguishing and after comparing the error ratio of the corresponding to (T) calculated, it was found that there were (3) paragraphs whose values were greater than (0.05), which indicates that they are not Distinctive, therefore, it was excluded (10, 25, 45) from the scale of openness to experience, and the number of its paragraphs became (60) paragraphs distributed among its fields, while the scale of self-control and following the same steps, (4) paragraphs were excluded (2, 20, 34 and 14). The number of its paragraphs (50) is divided into its fields.

Second: Internal consistency: The correlational relationship between the total score and the degree of each paragraph of the scale was extracted using the internal consistency method using the Pearson correlation coefficient by the statistical program (ssps) to find out the extent of the paragraph's relevance to the domain to which it belongs, and accordingly (4) paragraphs of the scale were excluded Openness to experience, and the scale consisted of (54) items. As for the self-control scale, (2) items were excluded, and the scale became (48) items.

Scientific coefficients for the two scales:

1. For the purpose of obtaining the stability of the two scales, the researchers used two methods, which are half segmentation and Vackronbach. A complete result was applied to Spearman Brown's law, and the result was for the measure of openness to experience (0.898) and for the scale of self-control (0.800). Thus, the two measures are constant.
2. Truthfulness: The truthfulness of the test is intended "to be an honest test when it measures the purpose for which it was set." (53: 1). And honesty consists of several types, and the researchers used the following types:

Apparent honesty: The experts agreed that these paragraphs are easy to formulate and clear, and their agreement is (75%) or more sufficient because it measures what it was prepared for.

The validity of the construct: which is sometimes called the sincerity of the concept and it is considered one of the most appropriate types of honesty because it depends on the empirical verification of the extent to which the scores of the paragraphs match the characteristic or concept to be measured, so this type of honesty has been achieved through the use of discriminatory power and internal consistency.

Objectivity of the scale: Objectivity means that the subjectivity of the researchers, their opinions and beliefs do not interfere with the test results completely (202: 6) and since the scale contains the correction key, it is considered objective.

Torsion coefficient: To know how close or far the sample is to the normal distribution, the researchers calculated the torsion coefficient, as its value was (0.46) for the openness to experience scale and (0.67) for the self-control scale.

Standard levels: The researchers chose five levels that were naturally distributed for the building sample of 100 (very good, good, average, acceptable, weak) and it appeared to us that the sample occurred at the average level.

The basic experiment: The two scales became ready to be applied to the application sample, consisting of (60) trainers, as the number of items of the openness to experience scale reached (56) items, and the number of items for the Self-Control Scale was (48) final items.

Statistical Methods: The researchers used the Statistical Package (SPSS) Sixteenth Edition.

Presentation, analysis and discussion of results:

Presenting, analyzing, and discussing the results of the openness to experience scale

Table (1) shows the arithmetic mean and standard deviations for the two measures of openness to experience and self-control

Domains	S	± A
Mental openness	43.2	8.98
Diverse activities	41.7	8.70
Feelings	40.9	8.85
Imagination	42.6	8.79
A measure of openness to experience	170.2	40.2
The ability to control	38.9	9.2
Potency	37.2	8.56
Reinforcement	31.8	7.89
Behaving in a good manner	39.4	8.66
Self-adjusting scale	151.8	33.11

Table (2) shows the levels for the two measures of openness to experience and self-control

percentage	number	Grades rough	Standard grades	Levels
				A measure of openness to experience
%5	3	236-280	60-80	very good
%20	12	192-235	56-67	good
%50	30	147-191	44-55	Average
%16.66	10	103-146	32-43	Acceptable
%8.33	5	56-102	20-31	Weak
				Self-adjusting scale
%5	3	202-240	69-80	very good
%20	12	164-201	57-68	good
%46.66	28	125-163	44-56	Average
%16.66	10	87-124	32-43	Acceptable
%11.66	7	55-86	20-31	Weak

This result can be explained in light of the characteristics of volleyball coaches and their abilities, continuous thinking and trying to address many of the complex knowledge tasks facing them in their work that require obtaining more knowledge, information and continuous communication with new, varied and distinct ideas from a behavioral or scientific point of view, reflecting Mental maturity, interest in culture, imagination and a willingness to deal with new ideas and non-traditional values, and enjoy the efficiency of emotions, and this is what was confirmed by Mahmoud Ibrahim (2001) a love of knowledge of the internal and external world alike, and its owner is rich in experiences and has a desire to think about unfamiliar things and values out of the ordinary He experiences positive and negative emotions higher than the closed individual (128: 8).

The sample members also enjoy self-control, and this is due to the methods of social upbringing in our society that are characterized by intolerance and complacency with the players in the event that they commit mistakes and socially unacceptable behaviors, in addition to the psychological, social and economic pressures that resulted from the circumstances of the successive harsh wars that the Iraqi individual was subjected to that

prompted By postponing the achievement of many goals and ambitions and continuing to strive to achieve them and not to surrender to the bitter reality and that the conditions of training and the suffering of coaches with players going through the stage of adolescence and guarantee the development of self-control and this is what was confirmed by Laila Abdul Razzaq (2002), as the profession of coaching requires a lot of selflessness from the one in charge of it. Defeat and surrender in front of difficult or troublesome situations and relinquishing many desires and immediate tendencies in order to achieve goals and complete training duties, which are essential factors for developing self-control (153: 3).

Presenting and analyzing the results of the correlation between the two measures of openness to experience and self-control.

Table (3) shows the mean, standard deviation, and r value of the two measures

mistake percentage	Value (t)	Self-tuning		Openness to experience	
		±A	S	±A	S
0.000	0.844	33.11	151.8	40.2	170.2

Table (3) shows that there is a significant correlation between the two measures of openness to experience and self-control among volleyball coaches. Researchers attribute that coaches seek intellectual interests for the sake of their purposes and have a mental openness to the training curriculum and new ideas and a desire to think of ideas far from the norm and they are willing to change their reform ideas And this is what Muhammad Saud (120: 5) confirmed by the social, economic and psychological conditions that have been produced by the conditions of suffering for a long time that push all groups of Iraqi society to cling to the future more than the present and strive to achieve their goals and aspirations, bypassing most of the restrictions imposed by these circumstances, but Coaches suffer from the conditions of bearing responsibility towards the family and the conditions of the profession, especially with players, and the consequent reduction of anger and aggression and the possession of transparent power to control himself and control his emotions and control them.

The researchers also attribute this to the nature of the relationship between openness to experience and self-control, as they form good relations with positive variables such as motivation to work, performance competence, self-realization and creativity. Creativity, when issued by the trainer, that trainer will be respected and appreciated in the eyes of his players and administrative bodies and the focus of attention for the media and thus be a good example. He is confident and proud and has restraint and control over his emotions in different playing situations during training and competition, as well as managing things wisely and with infinite sophistication, which makes the coach able to carry out his duties during training and competition, especially the volleyball game, which needs to make efforts in order to achieve goals and reach the athlete To the highest levels in addition to achieving achievements, as the coach has a great role to improve the psychological aspect of the players and to develop voluntary traits, moral values and self-confidence due to his personal characteristics that affect the player directly through control, psychological stability and lack of tension during matches and difficult situations and this was confirmed by NahidaResan (2002) There is an effective role that the coach plays in the players' digestion of psychological skills from Kh For the psychological preparation and individual characteristics of each player (9:25) Zaki Muhammad (1997) mentioned the effect of the coach's personality as effective in the level of performance and the player's personal response towards the coach that has a great impact on his creation (15: 2).

Conclusions and recommendations

Conclusions

1. The two current scales are a tool to reveal the level of openness to experience and self-control of volleyball coaches
2. The emergence of multiple levels in the level of openness to experience and self-control of volleyball coaches
3. The highest percentage obtained by the trainers within the levels of the two scales was on average.

Recommendations

1. The adoption of these two scales to measure openness to experience and self-control for volleyball coaches.
2. It is imperative that clubs provide equal opportunities for their coaches by holding scientific meetings and field visits to model clubs in order to communicate for more openness, harmony and awareness of them.

3. Conducting a study of openness to experience and its relationship to some variables such as aesthetic taste and some personality traits.
4. And between self-control and its relationship to some variables such as anxiety and depression.

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